

Advanced Shape Memory Hybrid Composites for Enhancing Crashworthiness

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ABSTRACT: Smart materials have drawn significant attention and interest in recent years. In particular, shape memory alloys (SMAs), a class of smart materials, are gaining importance in various fields: microsystems, biomedicine, robotics, aerospace and automotive. SMAs consist of two crystallographic phases, austenite and martensite. These types of materials can undergo large reversible deformations due to their capability of reversible phase transformation. One method utilised to exploit the exotic properties of SMAs is embedding such materials in the form of wires or continuous fibres, ribbons, or short fibres within a composite material, resulting in a hybrid smart composite. SMAs can present an attractive means for reducing stresses and deflections in the structures subjected to an impact, and they can generate significant tensile stresses. Furthermore, SMAs reinforced polymer composites have enormous potential as lightweight materials. In this direction, considering SMAs' superelastic effect, they are ideal candidates for energy-absorbing applications and the automotive industry. However, the integration of SMA composites for automotive structural components has not yet been fully explored and requires further investigation. The current study investigates innovative methods to incorporate SMAs within a composite material for an automotive structural component to enhance crashworthiness behaviour in the event of a collision. Numerical analysis of an SMA hybrid composite material, namely NiTi wire-impregnated carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP), for an automotive front structure crash box is initially considered, and subsequently, a full vehicle structure is evaluated. The materials' properties and the impact behaviours are simulated and verified by employing computational models discretised in LS-Dyna commercial explicit finite element analysis (FEA) software. The most relevant material models in Ls-Dyna are MAT_054/055 *MAT_ENHANCED_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE for composite materials and MAT_030 *MAT_SHAPE_MEMORY, which is ideal for the behaviour of the SMAs. Numerical results show the SMA's contribution in improving the specific energy absorption (SEA) and the stability of the crushing process progression in comparison to neat CFRP composites.

KEY WORDS: Shape-memory alloys, Smart composites, Finite element analysis (FEA), Crashworthiness, Automotive

1. Introduction

In today's era, technology plays a vital role in the thriving and emerging of more advanced materials known as smart materials. Smart materials, also called intelligent materials or adaptive materials [1], are defined as materials that have properties, shapes, and functions tailored to reacting to the surrounding environment and sensing stimulations [2, 3]. Smart materials have been under immense investigation; currently, the studies on smart materials are mostly performed in the medical, electronics, aerospace, and automotive fields [4]. Shape memory alloys (SMAs) are a class of smart materials that attracted the attention of researchers and engineers in the scientific field due to their peculiar and beneficial characteristics for a wide range of applications. For example, SMAs have the ability to change their shape and size with respect to temperature in a controlled manner [5]. Furthermore, the unique properties of SMAs prompted their inclusion to be considered for several automotive applications and opened the door for new possible and potential applications such as energy-absorbing components in vehicles structure.

1.1. Shape memory alloys (SMAs)

Shape memory alloys (SMAs) have physical and mechanical features that make them highly promising and advantageous candidates with significant potential for use in diverse fields such as aerospace, automotive, robotics, civil, and biomedical engineering [6, 7].

Shape memory alloys (SMAs) have the capacity to exhibit shape change with temperature variation. This is attributed to their thermo-mechanical properties and ability to reversible crystallographic phase transformation [8, 9], known as the shape memory effect, as shown in Figure 1. Another notable characteristic is their capability to recover large elastic strains, allowing the material to withstand substantial deformations. This phenomenon is known as pseudoelasticity [10](see Figure 1). One of the most common shape memory alloys in use is nickel-titanium (Nitinol or NiTi) alloys, composed of 45–50% titanium. However, several non-titanium alloys also have shape-memory properties, such as copper-zinc-aluminium and copper-aluminium-nickel alloys [11]. Nonetheless, the shape memory performance and

mechanical properties of these non-titanium alloys are limited compared to NiTi alloys [12].

Figure 1 Phase transformation in shape memory alloys

1.2. SMAs hybrid composites for automotive crashworthiness

Composites incorporating SMA are often referred to as smart composites [8]. Composite-based SMAs is one of the utilised methods to exploit the exotic properties of such materials where SMAs is embedded in the form of wires or continuous fibres, ribbons, or short fibres within a composite material [13, 14]. Many engineering applications are using SMA composites as smart structures.

Furthermore, when it comes to lightweight materials with exceptional properties, the use of reinforced polymer composites containing shape memory alloys (SMAs) holds enormous promise. The unique superelastic effect exhibited by SMAs makes them ideal candidates for a wide range of applications, particularly in energy-absorbing scenarios and the automotive industry, where their performance can be optimised. With their exceptional characteristics and versatility, SMAs-reinforced polymer composites are poised to significantly drive advancements in these fields [15, 16, 17].

Nevertheless, the full potential of integrating SMA composites into automotive structural components has not been thoroughly explored and requires further investigation. The current study aims to address this gap by proposing innovative methods to incorporate SMAs into composite materials for automotive structural components, with the goal of enhancing crashworthiness performance in the event of a collision. Specifically, numerical analysis is conducted on an SMA hybrid composite material, namely NiTi wire-impregnated carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP), for an automotive front structure crash box, followed by an assessment using a full vehicle structure. The material properties and impact behaviours are simulated using computational models

implemented in LS-Dyna, a commercial explicit finite element analysis (FEA) software. The most relevant material models in LS-Dyna are MAT_054/055 *MAT_ENHANCED_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE for composite materials and MAT_030 *MAT_SHAPE_MEMORY, which is ideal for the behaviour of the SMAs. The numerical findings demonstrate that the incorporation of SMAs leads to notable enhancements in specific energy absorption (SEA) and stability of the crushing process progression, surpassing the performance of neat CFRP composites.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Finite element modelling

For the numerical finite element (FE) modelling, LS-Dyna[®] solver is employed. A single-precision and symmetric multi-processing (SMP) LS-Dyna[®] version R12.0.0 is used. The geometry of the crash box depicted in Figure 2 is created under LS-DYNA FE software [18]. The full vehicle structure FE model in Figure 3 is based on a model developed by the National Crash Analysis Center. MAT_054/055 *MAT_ENHANCED_COMPOSITE_DAMAGE is considered for CFRP composite materials, and MAT_030 *MAT_SHAPE_MEMORY, for the behaviour of the SMAs. FEM characteristics and boundary conditions of the models are illustrated in Figure 2 and Figure 3. The pre and post-processor LS-PrePost[®] is employed to construct the keyword files and view the results.

Figure 2 Numerical model of the crash box impacted by a moving wall

Figure 3 FE model of the full vehicle structure

Figure 4 Different integrations of SMA with CFRP crash box

Figure 5 Integrations of SMA within the full vehicle structure

2.2. Methodology and Materials Properties

Considering first the crash box model, two types of SMA inclusion shapes, namely SMA wires and strips, and six configurations were examined, as shown in Figure 4. Three SMA volume fractions of $V_f = 0.01$, $V_f = 0.02$ and $V_f = 0.025$ were investigated, and the results were compared with

that of a neat CFRP crash box. Secondly, the full vehicle structure is considered, as illustrated in Figure 5. The SMA volume fractions considered for the full vehicle structure were $V_f = 0.015$ and $V_f = 0.03$ while the shape of the SMA inclusions was in the form of wires which was determined based on the resulting behaviour of the crash box. As for the utilised material properties, Table 1 illustrates the CFRP composite properties, and Table 2 shows the considered NiTi SMA properties.

Table 1 Material properties of T700/2510 CFRP [19]

ρ_o	CFRP density	1.52 g/cm ³
E_1	Longitudinal elastic modulus	127 GPa
E_2	Transverse elastic modulus	8.41 GPa
G_{12}	Shear modulus	4.21 GPa
ν_{12}	Major Poisson's ratio	0.309
ν_{21}	Minor Poisson's ratio	0.02049
x_T	Longitudinal tensile strength	2.20 GPa
y_T	Transverse tensile strength	48.9 MPa
x_C	Longitudinal compressive strength	1.47 GPa
y_C	Transverse compressive strength	199 MPa
s_C	Shear strength	154 MPa

Table 2 Material properties of SMA

ρ_l	SMA density	6.45 ^{a,b,c} g/cm ³
E_a	Elastic modulus at austenite phase	29.3 ^{a,b,c} GPa
E_m	Elastic modulus at martensite phase	29.3 ^{a,b,c} GPa
ν	Poisson's ratio	0.33 ^{d,e,f}
σ_S^{AS}	Start of the martensitic phase	790 ^{a,b} MPa
σ_F^{AS}	Finish of the martensitic phase	896 ^{a,b} MPa
σ_S^{SA}	Start of the austenitic phase	600 ^{a,b} MPa
σ_F^{SA}	Finish of the austenitic phase	450 ^{a,b} MPa
ϵ^L	Transformation strain	0.078 ^{a,b}

^a Meo et al. 2005 [20]

^b Guida et al. 2019 [21]

^c Gupta and Srivastav, 2010 [22]

^d Asadpoori et al. 2021 [23]

^e Auricchio et al. 2009 [24]

^f Iannucci et al. 2017 [25]

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 6 compares the different fragmentation behaviour for the crash box. It can be seen that the utilisation of SMA in the form of wires prevented or reduced the immediate fragmentation and scattering of CFRP debris upon impact. Furthermore, it allowed the structure to maintain its unity and continue to withstand the impact load as a cohesive entity. This behaviour was also observed in the case of the full vehicle structure when Figure 7 and Figure 8 are compared. This demonstrates that incorporating SMA wires improves CFRP composites' impact resistance and increases damage tolerance. However, the enhancement is not pronounced in the force-displacement curves shown in Figure 9 but is reflected by the absorbed energy-displacement behaviour as shown in Figure 10, where volume fractions of SMA wires $V_f = 0.01$, $V_f = 0.02$ and $V_f = 0.025$ resulted in increasing the energy absorption by 29.62, 57.71 and 106.6% respectively nevertheless almost unaffected when using the same volume fractions of SMA strips.

Figure 6 Fragmentation pattern of crash box

Figure 7 Fragmentation pattern of CFRP crash box within the full vehicle structure

Figure 8 Fragmentation pattern of hybrid SMA/CFRP crash box within the full vehicle structure

Figure 9 Force versus displacement of crash box

Additionally, weight-wise, the SEA yielded the same results indicating that utilising SMA wires would improve the crashworthiness and maintain the lightweight considerations for using the CFRP crash box. Considering the full vehicle structure, the level of energy absorption throughout the complete structure of the vehicle increased as well. SMA wires volume fractions of $V_f = 0.015$ and $V_f = 0.03$, improved the energy absorption by 4.55 and 9.05%, respectively. This enhanced energy absorption capacity would lead to improved safety and protection for passengers and reduce the risk of damage to the vehicle in case of accidents or collisions.

Figure 10 Energy absorption versus displacement of crash box

Figure 12 Energy absorption versus displacement of crash box within the full vehicle structure

Figure 11 Specific energy absorption (SAE) versus displacement of crash box

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, crashworthiness and safety are paramount considerations in the design and production of vehicles for passenger protection and minimal risk during collisions. Combining the unique properties of both composites and SMAs, the current research illustrates these advantages for automotive structures' behaviour from a mechanical perspective. Incorporating SMAs specifically in the form of wires into critical structural components like the crash box can effectively dissipate crash forces and maintain structural integrity during collisions. The energy absorption for the stand-alone crash box at SMA wires volume fractions $V_f = 0.01$, $V_f = 0.02$ and $V_f = 0.025$ resulted in increasing the energy absorption by 29.62, 57.71 and 106.6% respectively. For the full vehicle structure, the SMA wires volume fractions $V_f = 0.015$ and $V_f = 0.03$, have improved the energy absorption by 4.55 and 9.05%, respectively. Additionally, the exploitation of the lightweight nature of composites will not be compromised, as illustrated by the SEA results.

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